

INTERACTION OF HYDROXYACETOPHENONES AND THEIR DERIVATIVES WITH THIONYL CHLORIDE IN PRESENCE OF FINELY DIVIDED COPPER.

PART II. PREPARATION OF 3 : 3'-DIACETYL-4:6:4' : 6'-TETRAHYDROXYDIPHENYL THIOETHER AND ITS DERIVATIVES FROM RESACETOPHENONE

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The thioether of resacetophenone and its derivatives such as phenylhydrazone, oxime, semicarbazone, methoxy, ethoxy, acetoxy and benzyloxy are described and also its bromination, chlorination and nitration products.

It was observed by Hirwe, Jadhav and Chakradeo (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 101) that methyl salicylate gave bis-(3-carbomethoxy-4-hydroxyphenyl)-thioether when it was treated with thionyl chloride in presence of copper. The same authors (*J. Univ. Bom.*, 1933, 2, Part II, 128) obtained similar thioether from methyl 4-methoxysalicylate and from methyl 3-methylsalicylate and methyl 4-methylsalicylate (this *Journal*, 1934, 10, 551). Present work is the extension of that reaction to aromatic hydroxy-ketones.

The reaction was carried out in presence of dry chloroform, when a thioether was obtained. Its constitution was determined by the action of nitric acid on it in cold acetic acid medium, when 5-nitroresacetophenone was formed which showed that the two nuclei were linked together through sulphur atom in 5-position (*i. e.* *para* to OH group and *meta* to CO.Me group).

Bromination in acetic acid medium at room temperature gave a dibromo compound containing sulphur. These bromine atoms must have taken the position *ortho* to OH group and *meta* to both CO.Me group and sulphur atom, because it gave 3-bromo-5-nitroresacetophenone when it was treated with nitric acid in acetic acid medium. Excess of bromine solution gave 3 : 5-dibromoresacetophenone which further confirmed the constitution of the thioether and its dibromo derivative.

With sulphuryl chloride it gave dichlororesacetophenone which was given the constitution 3 : 5-dichlororesacetophenone by analogy with the bromination product. This clarified the constitution of *o,o*-dichlororesacetophenone described by Segalle (*Monatsh*, 1896, 17, 315) as it showed no lowering in melting point when mixed with this product.

Various characteristic derivatives of the thioether were prepared

EXPERIMENTAL

3:3'-Diacetyl-4:6:4' : 6'-tetrahydroxydiphenyl-thioether (I).—Resacetophenone (12 g.) was suspended in dry chloroform (20 c. c.), the mixture was surrounded with ice and thionyl chloride (20 g.) was gradually added. Copper powder (8 g.) was slowly added to the mixture at low temperature and the reaction was allowed to proce

overnight at room temperature. Next day more chloroform (20 c. c.) was added and heated under reflux on a water-bath at 60° for 5 minutes. The solution was filtered and the filtrate gave a sticky mass on removal of the solvent. The residue was washed with dry chloroform, dried and then extracted with dilute sodium hydroxide solution (3%). The alkaline extract was acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid, when pinkish solid was obtained. It crystallised from acetic acid in pinkish plates, m. p. 209-10°, yield 3 g. (Found : S, 10.0. $C_{16}H_{14}O_6S$ requires S, 9.6 per cent).

Its *phenylhydrazone* crystallised from acetic acid, m. p. 242-43°. (Found : N, 11.2. $C_{28}H_{26}O_4N_4S$ requires N, 10.9 per cent).

Its *oxime* crystallised from dilute alcohol in white needles, m. p. 228-29°. (Found : N, 7.6. $C_{16}H_{16}O_6N_2S$ requires N, 7.7 per cent).

Its *semicarbazone* melts at 285° (decomp.). (Found : N, 18.3. $C_{16}H_{20}O_6N_6S$ requires N, 18.7 per cent).

3:3'-Diacetyl-4:6:4':6'-tetraethoxydiphenyl-thioether.—Methylation was carried out with dimethyl sulphate by heating the mixture on a boiling water-bath for 1 hour. It crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 196-97°. (Found : S, 8.4. $C_{20}H_{22}O_8S$ requires S, 8.2 per cent).

3 : 3'-Diacetyl-4 : 6 : 4' : 6'-tetraethoxydiphenyl-thioether.—Ethylation was carried out with ethyl iodide in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate in dry acetone medium by boiling the mixture for 24 hours. After removal of the solvent potassium carbonate was removed by water and unchanged thioether by dilute sodium hydroxide solution. It crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 152-53°. (Found : S, 7.6. $C_{24}H_{30}O_8S$ requires S, 7.2 per cent).

3:3'-Diacetyl-4:6:4':6'-tetraacetoxydiphenyl-thioether.—Acetylation was carried out by boiling the thioether for 3 hours with acetic anhydride in presence of pyridine. It crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 146-47°. (Found : S, 6.5. $C_{24}H_{22}O_{10}S$ requires S, 6.4 per cent).

3:3'-Diacetyl-4:4'-dihydroxy-6:6'-dibenzoyloxydiphenyl-thioether was prepared by heating the mixture of the thioether, benzoyl chloride and pyridine on a boiling water-bath for 4 hours. It crystallised from acetic acid in pinkish plates, m. p. 228-29°. (Found : S, 6.3. $C_{30}H_{22}O_8S$ requires S, 5.9 per cent).

It showed no depression in melting point when mixed with the thioether obtained from 2 : 2'-dihydroxy-4 : 4'-dibenzoyloxyresacetophenone.

3:3'-Diacetyl-4:6:4':6'-tetrahydroxy-5:5'-dibromodiphenyl-thioether.—The thioether (1, 1 g.) was dissolved in 3-4 c. c. of boiling acetic acid and 15% solution of bromine in acetic acid (8 c. c.) was slowly added to it when the solution was at 60° and then it was shaken for 1 hour and then left over. After about 6 hours the crystalline solid separating was filtered and recrystallised from acetic acid in brown plates, m. p. 232-33°. (Found : Br, 32.2. $C_{16}H_{12}O_6Br_2S$ requires Br, 32.5 per cent).

3 : 5-Dibromoresacetophenone.—The thioether (1, 0.5 g.) was dissolved in 2 c. c. of boiling acetic acid and 15% solution of bromine in acetic acid (15 c. c.) was added when the solution was at 50°. The mixture was left overnight at room temperature and then diluted with water and the product finally crystallised from alcohol in pinkish needles, m. p. 173-74°. (Found : Br, 51.5. $C_8H_6O_3Br_2$ requires Br, 51.6 per cent).

The same substance was also obtained from 3:3'-diacetyl-4:6:4':6'-tetrahydroxy-5:5'-dibromodiphenyl-thioether by bromination with more bromine solution. Dahse (*Ber.*, 1908, 41, 1621) gave m.p. 173-74°.

5-Nitroresacetophenone.—To the thioether (I, 1 g.) concentrated nitric acid (d 1.42) was very slowly added. The reaction mixture was left at room temperature for about 3 hours and then poured over crushed ice, when a solid was obtained. It was finally crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 142°. (Found: N, 7.5. $C_8H_7O_2N$ requires N, 7.1 per cent). Baker (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1691) gave m.p. 142°.

The same substance is obtained if the reaction is carried out in presence of glacial acetic acid at room temperature.

3:5-Dinitroresacetophenone.—The thioether (I, 1 g.) was dissolved in acetic acid (5 c.c.) and nitric acid (conc., 10 c.c.) was added to it. After about an hour the reaction mixture was heated on a boiling water-bath for about 40 minutes and worked up as before. Yellow crystals were obtained from alcohol, m.p. 166-67°. (Found: N, 11.8. $C_8H_6O_2N_2$ requires N, 11.6 per cent). Roger Adams (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 41, 265) gave m.p. 166-67°.

3-Bromo-5-nitroresacetophenone.—3:3'-Diacetyl-4:6:4':6'-tetrahydroxy-5:5'-dibromodiphenyl-thioether was treated with concentrated nitric acid in presence of acetic acid and the reaction mixture was left overnight at room temperature. It was worked up as before. It crystallised from acetic acid in yellow plates, m.p. 182-83°. (Found: N, 5.4. $C_8H_6O_2NBr$ requires N, 5.1 per cent).

3:5-Dichlororesacetophenone.—The thioether (I, 1 g.) was dissolved in dry ether, sulphuryl chloride (2 c.c.) added and then a crystal of bismuth chloride was added as a catalyst. The reaction mixture was left at room temperature for two days. After removal of the ether brownish needles were obtained. It crystallised from benzene in white needles, m.p. 195-96°. (Found: Cl, 31.7. $C_8H_6O_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 32.1 per cent).

This gave no lowering in melting point of the substance described as *ω*-dichlororesacetophenone by Segalle (*loc. cit.*).

Semicarbazone crystallised from alcohol in brownish plates, m.p. above 285°. (Found: N, 15.4. $C_9H_9O_2N_3Cl_2$ requires N, 15.1 per cent).